

The Role of Organizational Culture in Improving the Green Supply Chain: An Exploratory Research in Al-Ittihad Food Industries Company Limited

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Abstract:

The Research Aims To Identify The Role Of Organizational Culture In Improving The Green Supply Chain Of The Union Company For Food Industries In Babil Governorate, And In Order To Achieve This, The Dimensions Of Organizational Culture (Relationships, Goals, Rewards) Were Adopted, And The Dimensions Of The Green Supply Chain (Purchase) Were Adopted. Green, Green Manufacturing, Green Marketing, Green Design), And Al-Ittihad Company For Food Industries Limited Was Chosen As One Of The Largest Food Industry Companies In Iraq As An Exploratory And Analytical Field For Research By Distributing A Questionnaire That Included (78) Respondents From The Administration Managers, Heads Of Departments, Divisions And Their Units For Factories The Research Sample, And One Of The Most Important Conclusions Reached By The Research Is That The Organizational Culture Effectively Affects The Promotion Of The Green Supply Chain Of The Organization. The Research Sample In Light Of The Great Competition In The Food Industry Sector In Iraq. Organizational In Enhancing The Positive Impact Relationship Between It And The Dimensions Of The Dependent Variable Of The Green Supply Chain Within The Industrial Sector And In Line With Continuing To Create Products Of Strategic Value For Industrial Enterprises And Achieving Environmental Sustainability By Keeping Abreast Of Developments And Seizing Opportunities To Ensure Continuity, Growth And Survival In The Labor Market.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Green Supply Chain

1. Introduction

Organizational culture plays an important and pivotal role in the formation of the distinctive personality of the organization, which gives it its own character that is different from the rest of the competitors, which can be likened to the thumbprint of ordinary individuals, meaning that there is no organization similar to any other organization in existence, even if the rest of the organizations try to imitate it, there will be aspects that are impossible for the rest Organizations apply them identically from the organization and thus this privacy is reflected in the goods and services provided by the organization to achieve a competitive advantage that is distinct from the rest of the goods and services of other organizations and is sustainable. Hence the growing importance of organizational culture, especially in today's world and the dynamic environment that is accelerating with changes in all fields and sectors, including environmental sustainability that It has become one of the most important elements affecting the work of business organizations as an

urgent necessity due to the emergence of climate problems such as global warming and the devastating effects it generates such as massive hurricanes and others.

2. Methodology

2-1 Research problem

The current research problem can be formulated in the form of questions as follows:

a. What is the level of availability of organizational culture dimensions in the researched organization?

B- What is the level of availability of the green supply chain dimensions of the researched organization?

c. What is the nature of the relationship between the variables of the current research, which is the organizational culture and the green supply chain?

T. What is the nature of the impact of organizational culture on the green supply chain?

2-2 The importance of research

The importance of the research follows from the nature of the variables dealt with in the current research, namely the organizational culture and the green supply chain, both of which represent two variables; They are very important and necessary for any organization that seeks to achieve renewal and keep abreast of the rapid global and local developments in the current era, as well as its quest for growth and prosperity and to ensure the continuity of its existence in a competitive environment characterized by a lot of uncertainty and instability. And how to invest it and employ its outputs of ideas in promoting the green supply chain to achieve environmental sustainability. The solution to the problem lies by answering the following questions:

1- What is the nature of the relationship between the organizational culture and the green supply chain within the work of the researched organization?

2- Is there an effect of the organizational culture in achieving the elements of the green supply chain?

3-2 Research objectives

The current research seeks to achieve the following:

a. Identify the interest of the research sample organizations in the dimensions of organizational culture.

B. Determine the level of interest of the departments of the research sample organizations in the importance of applying the green supply chain.

T. Identify the nature and type of relationship between the two research variables.

w. Measuring the level of influence of organizational culture on the green supply chain.

Research hypothesis

According to what was mentioned in the research problem and in order to achieve the objectives envisaged by it, the following main hypothesis was formulated: (There is a significant effect of organizational culture in the green supply chain), and four sub-hypotheses branch out from it:

- There is a significant effect of the organizational culture in the green marketing dimension.
- There is a significant impact of organizational culture in the dimension of green design
- There is a significant effect of the organizational culture in the green purchasing dimension
- There is a significant effect of the organizational culture in the green industrialization dimension.

5-2 Research Limits

Temporal limits: The time limits of the research extended from November 2022 to July 2023.

Spatial boundaries: represented by the Union Company for Food Industries Ltd. in Babil Governorate.

Human limits: The research sample included (a random sample) of the administration managers and heads of departments, divisions and units of the company, the research sample, and (78) questionnaires were distributed, while the number of retrieved and valid forms for analysis reached (68) forms, i.e. with a retrieval rate of 87%

The first topic - the theoretical framework of the research

First: Organizational Culture

1- Concept Of Organizational Culture:

Recent years have witnessed tremendous developments in management thought in general, and since the year 1990 organizational culture has begun to play a crucial role in organizational sustainability research. The past focused on achieving profits alone, and in order to pursue organizational sustainability towards a successful transformation, business organizations need to create an organizational culture of sustainability (Ketprapakorn & Kantabutra, 2022,640), which led to the accumulation of extensive knowledge and practical experience in business organizations, while it is recognized It is widely accepted that organizational culture is critical in ensuring corporate sustainability (Ketprapakorn & Kantabutra, 2022,638), and organizational culture is a set of standards or values widely applied to an organization, and organizational culture in an organization cannot be underestimated because it plays a role in giving identity organization, which states that organizational culture is a symbol of unspoken communication between members of the organization (Ferine et al, 2021,2), and culture can be understood as an explicit social product that arises from social interaction as an intended or unintended consequence of behaviour (Kareem, 2022,1). Organizational culture is a pattern of beliefs, values and rituals that affect the behaviour of all individuals and groups within the organization and control the members of the organization through interaction with each other and with suppliers, customers and other people outside the organization, which means that it is a systems of values and beliefs for working individuals that are developed from Before the organization so that it leads the behaviour of the members of the organization itself (Srikaningsih & Setyadi, 2015,211), and organizational culture can be defined as the basic values, protocols, beliefs and assumptions that are rooted in the structure of organizations and that are maintained by the members of the organizations and in a way that proves and reinforces those basic principles (Bagga et al, 2022,3).

Importance Of Organizational Culture:

Organizational culture plays an important role in the success and failures of organizations, as organizational culture provides employees with a framework that they can apply to reality, which helps them evaluate what is important to the organization and themselves, and what is irrelevant to the organization so as to be successful in changing strategy, for example, such as the trend towards more From sustainability first, change in organizational culture is inevitable. (Rass et al,2023,3), as well as organizational culture is a pattern of rationale for enabling members of the organization to overcome problems by adapting from the external environment and integrating into the organization so that employees From working as required (Fachruddin & Sri Yanti, 2020,18), it is known that culture has a role in creating distinctive differences for the organization that distinguishes it from other organizations. On the other hand, culture brings a sense of identity to the members of the organization and acts as a mechanism for making meaning and control that

directs and shapes attitudes and behaviors of employees (Mandi & Harsono, 2019, 35), and organizational culture contributes to maintaining a positive work environment as well as to the effectiveness of organizational performance. Organizational culture in the organization because it plays an important role in giving the distinctive identity of the organization (Ferine et al, 2022, 2), organizational culture is one of the most important features of effectiveness because it defines the standards and values of the organization in addition to that it forms culture in organizations and provides a better understanding of its effectiveness. Therefore, organizational culture is associated with organizational effectiveness (Naveed et al, 2022,3).

3- Characteristics Of Organizational Culture:-

The (Denison) model indicated that the best-performing organizations had high levels of four cultural traits, namely: - (Bagga et al, 2022,3):

A- The culture of participation / helps superior companies develop their companies around team members, facilitate coordinated activities, and empower and involve their employees. Managers, executives, and employees are committed and feel a strong sense of ownership towards organizational values. This participation feature constitutes a set of values that emphasize the organization's ability to respond to changes and flexibility in the environment. Business.

B- A consistent culture that provides a central source of coordination, communication, integration and control for systems development. This culture is realized in organizations with a high degree of consistency among team members who are committed to a distinguished practice of business performance. In order to promote behaviours consistent with core values, a clear code of conduct is established with roles and instructions. Strong, this trait serves as a strong source of internal integration and a high level of matching to balance workforce stability and transparent communication

C- The culture of ability / and shows the extent of the ability to adapt in the organization that creates change to analyze the company's environment externally and focuses on customers, and cares for them, and this feature forms a group with a culture of participation that focuses on flexibility.

D- Mission Culture: Has a strong sense of future directions with clear goals and vision. When the mission changes, the different aspects of the organizational culture appear, and also the organizations that score high marks for the mission culture will deal with their external business environment through stabilization.

4- Dimensions Of Organizational Culture

There is no difference in dimensions in many research variables, such as what we see in the dimensions of organizational culture because of the breadth and complexity of the topic. The researchers have dealt with it each according to its environment and the starting points that it deems appropriate, but there is some agreement on a set of dimensions, which are (Raouf, 393: 2021).

Woszczyzna, 2014, 31))

- Relationships: in order to develop skills through intensive training programs and work flexibility
- Rewards: Material and moral incentives to push towards the implementation of the organization's goals
- Goals: realistic and executable plans through the components of creativity

- Knowledge: the appropriate area and fields of scientific research
- Sources: Good timing for appropriate funding sources
- Risks: Availability of appropriate budget, required support and learning for the future to meet challenges

The dimensions of relationships, rewards and goals have been adopted for their suitability to the work environment in the current research field.

Second: - Green Supply Chain:

1- Supply Chain:-

The concept of supply chain management has attracted a great deal of interest among academics and practitioners alike over the past two decades due to the fact that supply chain management is key to company performance. Customers and internal operational practices with the aim of enhancing the level of their competitiveness and performance in addition to customer satisfaction (Lagat et al, 2016,3), and the recent decades are characterized by a significant development in supply chain management in academic research and administrative practices due to the interest of companies in controlling costs and improving the quality of services provided to customers by By reducing response times to requests (Abdrahamane et al, 2018,222), nowadays companies have to face changing environments where technology becomes out dated more quickly and consumers demand more differentiated products and services, in addition to that and with increasing competition, they must be more aware With changes in the design of products and services (Diaz & Ping, 2018, 23), the supply chain is a system of people, activities, information and resources involved in creating a product and then transferring it to the customer, and it consists of all parties involved, directly or indirectly, in fulfilling the customer's request and does not include the supply chain only Manufacturers and suppliers, but also carriers, warehouses, retailers, and even customers themselves (Al-Madi, 2017,150),

Supply chain management is usually seen as located between vertically integrated companies where the entire material flow is owned by one company and those in which each member of the channel operates independently so coordination between the various players in the chain is key in its effective management (Junaidi, 2017). ,73)

, Supply chain management is the integration of the activities of procurement of materials and services, conversion into semi-finished goods and finished products, and delivery to customers (Ramadiyanto & Augustine, 2019,183),

2- Importance Of The Supply Chain:-

Companies face an unpredictable environment characterized by rapid changes in technologies, as well as great differentiation in customer demand, strong differences in the supply of materials, and unexpected changes in the competitive environment. The success of companies depends on their ability to deal with these changes. Therefore, most of these companies have adopted many practices such as Timely delivery, process re-engineering, quality management and automation to remain competitive in its markets (Abuzaid, 2014,167), supply chain management integrates all business links and processes involved in it through an information management system and the application of artificial intelligence algorithms to the supply chain management system that can To help companies effectively reduce operating costs and improve their ability to respond to market demands and thus increase overall operational efficiency (Lin et al, 2022,1), supply chain management is the integration of all activities associated with the flow and transfer of goods from

the stage of raw materials, to the end user, as well as the information associated with it by improving relations between and within companies to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage and the practice of supply chain management meets the basic requirements that make the company alive in the competitive global race and also achieve profit and the success of the organization depends first on the performance of supply chains in which the organization is a partner and depends. The performance of the supply chain also depends on the capabilities of the supply chain partners to adapt to the dynamics of the external environment (Obi et al, 2020,1), in the case of logistics management, reliability leads to the ability to deliver the product, in the right place, at the right time, under packing conditions required, in quantity, documents and with the excellent client in a correct manner (Abdrahamane et al, 2019,171).

3- The Main Functions Of Supply Chain Management:-

The purpose of supply chain management is to improve trust and cooperation among supply chain partners, thus improving the movement, visibility and speed of inventory. The main functions of supply chain management are as follows (NJOKU & O.U., 2015,235):

- Inventory Management
- Distribution management
- Channel management
- Payment management
- financial management
- Supplier management
- Transportation management
- Customer Service Management

4- Green Supply Chain:-

At the global level, there is awareness of shifting to greener models of means of production and supply chain. However, even emerging economies have developed their own individual pathways to awareness of its importance. There are several studies conducted specifically among emerging economies to draw attention towards different aspects of green supply chain, and one of these aspects is connectivity. Between the roles of customers and the reduction of plastic consumption, in which awareness of the environmentally hostile effects of plastic uses and the use of social media to spread awareness is crucial (Saini et al, 2023,2), and business organizations seek to gain a competitive advantage through sustainable development such as the introduction of innovation. In production and improving environmental protection measures by complying with international regulations such as green marketing certification, adopting environmentally friendly lean systems, following policies to address customer concerns about the environment, and minimizing the environmental impact of production and service activities (Zhang, 2022,1), and manufacturing companies are not responsible. Not only preserving the environment and reducing levels of environmental pollution, but also including its commercial partners in the supply chain to achieve these goals, and consumer expectations force companies with regard to changes in the climate such as pollution and others to create supply chains that improve environmental sustainability (Rodríguez-González et al. al ,2022,1), and reflects the company's performance in improving its supplies to manage the chain to reduce the use of materials, energy or water required in production processes and to find more environmentally efficient solutions (Ullah et al,2022,2), so the development and management of processes related to products and services has become more

It is complicated by globalization and how the supply chain perspective can support the development of more sustainable consumption and production patterns, taking into account the diversity of stakeholders in the supply chain and those involved in sustainability challenges (Fritz,2022,2).

5- Dimensions Of The Green Supply Chain:-

Most researchers agreed that the green supply chain consists of four dimensions (Eliting 2009), (Al-Taie, 2012) and (Weeratunge & Herath, 2018:60-61), which are (green purchasing, green manufacturing, green design, green manufacturing). The following is an explanation of the dimensions Green Supply Chain:-

A- Green Procurement: Green procurement is defined as "the positive choice and acquisition of products and services that more effectively reduce the negative environmental impacts on their life cycle from manufacturing, transportation, use, recycling or disposal, and among the features that must be included in green products and services is their ability Conserving energy and water as well as reducing the generation of waste and the release of pollutants, and can be recycled (Dubey et al, 2013:188), green purchasing is also called sustainable purchasing and is defined as the purchase of any product and service that results in minimal negative environmental impact and the use of price as a comparable standard To demonstrate social and ethical responsibility, the purchasing department needs to strike a balance between quality, cost, functionality, environment, and social and ethical aspects in order to purchase a product or service in response to the increased concern for environmental sustainability (Chin et al, 2020:292).

B- Green manufacturing: The phrase green manufacturing or sustainable manufacturing is used to describe procedures related to characterizing and reducing the negative environmental impacts of manufacturing. Therefore, sustainability involves much more than a simple act of analyzing and modifying the environmental performance of manufacturing processes and systems (Paul et al, 2014: 1646). And green manufacturing means environmental awareness in manufacturing and its complementary functions such as the scope of employment, a broader amount of green and renewable energy sources, and participation in green supply chains (D'Angelo et al, 2022:1901)

C - Green design: - It is called sustainable design, and in order to achieve green design, elements such as quality (Q), cost (C), etc. are required in product design, to maximize the use of resources and reduce environmental pollution, in order to achieve value maximization and cost reduction. Green design should not only focus on "man", but also respect nature, that is, seek harmony between man and nature, coexistence, and embody the "unity of nature and man". Therefore, green design aims to achieve sustainability to reach economic and social development (YUAN & Tang ,2021:1).

D- Green Marketing: The term "green marketing" appeared for the first time under the name "environmental marketing", which was "concerned with all marketing activities that try to avoid causing environmental problems and work in a way that is able to provide a remedy for those problems (prieto-Sandoval, 2022: 3), and the concept of green marketing relates to protecting the ecological environment and explains how brands have begun to change their tasks and practices from revenue-driven to environmentally conscious through business operations that have the least possible negative impact on the environment (Kanyuiro & Maina, 2020:64), and many business organizations found that internal green marketing strategy and approach has a significant impact on environmental competitiveness (Ismail et al,2023:2).

Practical Side

First: Description Of The Research Sample

The Union Company for Food Industries was chosen as a research community. As for the sample size, it reached (68) workers distributed over (6) factories, divisions, and divisions of the factory. As (78) questionnaires were distributed, and the number of questionnaires retrieved was (68) form.

Table (1) Description of the research sample

T	Variants	Categories	Issue	Percentage ratio
1	Social gender	Male	55	81%
		Female	13	19%
		Total	68	100%
2	:Age group	years old 30 - 18	3	4%
		years old 39-30	27	40%
		years old 49-40	18	26%
		years old 59-50	15	22%
		years and over 60	5	8%
	Total	68	100%	
3	Academic qualification	Ph. D. in	2	3%
		Masters	6	9%
		Higher diploma	5	7%
		Bachelor	36	53%
		Institute	16	24%
	Junior high and above	3	4%	
4	Service life	Total	68	100%
		Less than 10 years	38	56%
		years 15 - 10	13	19%
		years old 20 - 16	17	25%
	Total	68	100%	

Source: Prepared by the researcher

From the outputs of Table (1), it is clear that the characteristics of the sample members of the research sample are as follows:

1- Social Gender: The statistical results presented in Table (1) showed that the majority of the sample were males, as it reached (81%), which is equivalent to (55) individuals, while the percentage of females was (19%), which is equivalent to (13) out of the total sample, which means that the percentage of males is more than three times compared to females.

2- The age group: The statistical results presented in Table (1) showed that the rate of (40%) was for the age group (30-39 years) and (26%) was for the age group ranging from (40-49 years). (22%) were for the age group ranging from (50-59 years), and (4%) were for the age groups (18-30 years), and (8%) were for the age groups (60 years and over), which indicates that The strength of the organization's tendency is the research sample to rely on the ages of those whose categories are in the twenties, thirties and forties of age, which is a good percentage for working in the factories of the Union Food Industries Company because most jobs require muscular effort and high activity, as this category reflects the level of awareness, awareness and maturity.

3- Academic qualification: Table (1) shows the distribution of the respondents according to their educational attainment, and the largest percentage of respondents who hold a bachelor's degree was (53%), and then the percentage of respondents who hold an institute certificate, as their percentage reached (24%) As for the third place, the percentage of respondents who held a master's degree was ranked, which amounted to (9%), and then in the fourth place, it was the holders of a higher diploma with a percentage of (7%) and a preparatory certificate, which amounted to (4%). Finally, the doctorate certificate came with a percentage of (3% only. By looking at the above percentages, it is clear that the majority of the sample are holders of degrees and have academic and practical experience, and this indicates the ability to complete the work in a distinguished and innovative way in order to carry out the work entrusted to them efficiently and effectively.

4- Duration of service: - Through the results of table (1), it is clear to us that the largest percentage of the research sample was for the category (less than 10 years), as their percentage reached (56%). As for those whose years of service ranged from (10-15 years), it reached Their percentage is (19%), and then for the category (16-20 years) at a rate of (25%). These percentages indicate that the majority of the respondents have significant functional experience in the organization.

Secondly. Evaluation of the quality and conformity of the criteria used in the research

a. Assessment of the quality and conformity of organizational culture variable questions

We notice in Table (2) the external ramifications and the Wackeronbach coefficient for the questions of the organizational culture variable, which consists of three basic dimensions consisting of (10) paragraphs, as the model will be tested within the following indicators:

- Through Table (2), we see the CR values of the composite stability variable of organizational culture, which are all within acceptable limits, as they ranged between (0.8309-0.8505). It is a good indicator and indicates the stability of the scale, as the results showed a high stability of the organizational culture variable.

- From table (2), we see that the value of the Alpha Cronbach coefficient for all dimensions has a coefficient greater than (0.71), and this indicates that the coefficient of reliability and reliability of the measurement tool has a high degree of stability.

- It appears through the values of the external bifurcations of the scale questions for the organizational culture variable are close to greater than the acceptable minimum limits of (0.71), as the external bifurcation values ranged between (0.628-0.815), which indicates that the data on the organizational culture variable are characterized by stability and reliability. Suitable for conducting subsequent statistical analyses, as all of them exceeded the significant values of the ramifications, which is a good indicator. It should be noted here that some questions had

ramifications less than (0.71), and because they were significant, when deleting them, the researcher found that they did not affect the validity of the model. Based on this result, they were kept within the form.

- Table (2) shows the values of the extracted average variance (AVE) for the organizational culture variable, as it turns out that all of them are acceptable because all dimensions are greater than (0.54), as they all indicate approximate validity, which is a good indicator.

Table (2) Statistical indicators for the organizational culture variable

T	Dimensions	Paragraphs	Bifurcations	Cronbach Alpha	Composite	AVE
1	Relationships X	Q1	0.628	0.7502	0.8440	0.577
		Q2	0.694			
		Q3	0.810			
		Q4	0.808			
2	Goals X2	Q5	0.753	0.7279	0.8309	0.555
		Q6	0.725			
		Q7	0.695			
3	Rewards X3	Q8	0.604	0.7308	0.8505	0.664
		Q9	0.883			
		Q10	0.815			

Source: prepared by the researcher based on the SmartPLS program P .Quality

B. Evaluation of the quality and conformity of green supply chain variable questions

We see through Table (2) the external ramifications and the Wackeronbach coefficient for the questions of the green supply chain variable, which consists of four basic dimensions consisting of (14) items, as the model will be tested within the following indicators:

- Table (3) shows the composite stability values (CR) for the green supply chain variable, which are all within acceptable limits, as it ranged between (0.8615-0.9126), which is a good indicator, as the results showed a high stability of the research scale questions for the green supply chain variable.

- The results showed that the value of the Alpha Cronbach coefficient ranged between (0.7994-0.8842), as it is clear that it is greater than (0.71), and this indicates that the coefficient of validity and stability of the measurement tool has a high degree of acceptance and stability.
- It appears through the values of the external ramifications of the scale questions of the green supply chain variable, as its values ranged between (0.411- 0.893), which indicates that the data of the green supply chain variable are characterized by stability and reliability and are suitable for conducting subsequent statistical analyzes, as all of them exceeded the significant values of the ramifications, which is a good indicator. It should be noted here that some of the questions had ramifications less than (0.71), and because they were significant, and when deleting them, the researcher found that they did not affect the validity of the model. Based on this result, they were kept within the model.
- We also note the values of the extracted average variance (AVE) for the strategic creativity variable, as it turns out that all of them are acceptable, as they ranged between (0.544-0.717), which is greater than the value (0.52), as they all indicate the convergent validity of the dimensions, which is a good indicator.

Table (3) Statistical indicators for the green supply chain variable

T	Dimensions	Paragraphs	Bifurcations	Cronbach Alpha h	Compound stability	AVE
1	Green buying	Q11	0.840	0.8842	0.9126	0.585
		Q12	0.893			
		Q13	0.773			
		Q14	0.866			
2	Green manufacturing	Q15	0.411	0.8547	0.8918	0.544
		Q16	0.683			
		Q17	0.829			
		Q18	0.806			
3	Green marketing	Q19	0.518	0.7994	0.8615	0.564
		Q20	0.795			

		Q21	0.768			
4	Green design	Q22	0.813	0.8006	0.8831	0.717
		Q23	0.832			
		Q24	0.891			

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the Smar tPLS program

. Descriptive analysis

This research attempts to describe and diagnose the opinions of the research sample about its adopted variables, as well as presenting the data shown by the questionnaire and analyzing the sample's responses regarding the independent variable, organizational culture and its dimensions (relationships X1, goals X2, rewards X3), and the dependent variable which is the green supply chain and its dimensions (purchasing Green Y1, green manufacturing Y2, green packaging Y3, green design Y4). Tables of the frequency distributions of the research variables have been prepared and approved for the purposes of the statistical analysis process and to obtain the weighted arithmetic mean, standard deviations, and percentage weights to find out the intensity of the answer achieved from the point of view of the mentioned sample members. To the degree obtained and related to the responses of the sample.

• Description and diagnosis of the independent variable (Organizational Culture X)

We see through table (4) the descriptive statistics of the independent research variable (organizational culture), noting that the hypothetical arithmetic mean of the scale of (3) was mainly used to know the extent to which the research sample was aware of the research variables: The following is a detailed explanation of the opinions of the research sample on the dimensions of organizational culture:

a. Relationships X1: It is noted from the results of Table (4) that the weighted arithmetic mean for the dimension of the relationships amounted to (3.552) with a standard deviation of (1.14) and a coefficient of difference (0.33). Research (70%), and this indicates that the (relationships) dimension is of great importance in the researched organization. We see in this table that the weighted arithmetic mean of all the paragraphs of the relationships is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3). Paragraph (2) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, as it reached (3.70), with a standard deviation (1.15), a coefficient of variation (0.31), and the intensity of the answer (70.9%, which indicates the consistency of the research sample's answers to this paragraph, compared to the rest of the dimensions. While paragraph (4) got the lowest weighted arithmetic mean, it was (3.35), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean (3) with a standard deviation (1.17), a coefficient of difference (0.36), and the intensity of the answer (67.1%), which means that the management of the organization encourages workers In engaging in positive relationships between each other and customers.

B. Goals X2: The weighted arithmetic mean of the goals dimension was (3.47). And the value of the arithmetic mean is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean, and this indicates the possession of goals that enable identifying opportunities and seizing them to the maximum extent. It indicates the views of the research sample regarding the aforementioned dimension. The percentage of the intensity of the answer for the members of the research sample was (69.3%), and this indicates that the goal dimension is one of the clear dimensions for the members of the research sample as it

is one of the important dimensions of organizational culture. Through the table, we also see that the weighted arithmetic mean of all items of the entrepreneurial mentality dimension is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3). Paragraph (3) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, reaching (3.68), with a standard deviation of (1.12), a coefficient of variation (0.31), and intensity The answer is (73.5%), which indicates the consistency of the research sample's answers to this paragraph. Paragraph (1) obtained the lowest weighted arithmetic mean, as it reached (3.23), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean (3), with a standard deviation of (1.35), a coefficient of difference (0.40), and the intensity of the answer (64.9%), and this indicates that the goals are important. large in the sample.

c. Rewards X3: Respondents were asked three items in this dimension. It appears from table (4) that the weighted arithmetic mean of all paragraphs after rewards was higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3). Paragraph (1) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, as it reached (3.92), with a standard deviation of (0.98) and a coefficient of variation (0.25).) and the intensity of the answer (78.4%), which indicates the consistency of the research sample's answers to this paragraph. The total weighted arithmetic mean for the rewards dimension was (3.547) with a standard deviation of (1.11) and a coefficient of difference (0.31). This means that the management of the organization has an effective system of rewards and incentives, which constitutes a strong motivation for the employees to perform their work in an excellent manner.

At the macro level, the organizational culture variable achieved a weighted arithmetic mean of (3.529). The value of the arithmetic mean is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean, which means, in actual terms, the strength of the availability of organizational culture dimensions in the organization, the research community, and what supports this is that the standard deviation reached (1.157), which is a small value that indicates the convergence of the research sample's answers regarding organizational culture. The intensity of the answer was (70.41%).

Table (4) Description and diagnosis of organizational culture

	Questions	Arithmetic mean	Severity of the answer	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
1	Q1	3.64	72.8%	1.16	0.32
2	Q2	3.70	70.9%	1.15	0.31
3	Q3	3.51	70.2%	1.12	0.32
4	Q4	3.36	67.1%	1.17	0.36
x1	X1 relationships	3.552	70.25%	1.15	0.33
1	Q5	3.23	64.8%	1.35	0.40
2	Q6	3.55	71.9%	1.15	0.32
3	Q7	3.68	73.5%	1.12	0.31
x2	Goals X2	3.49	70.07%	1.21	0.34
1	Q9	3.92	78.4%	0.98	0.25
2	Q10	3.45	69.0%	1.11	0.32
3	Q11	3.27	65.4%	1.13	0.34
x3	X3 rewards	3.547	70.9%	1.11	0.31
X	Organizational	3.529	70.41%	1.157	0.327

	culture X				
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Source: Prepared by the researcher based on Excel

Table (5) shows the arrangement of organizational culture dimensions based on relative importance. Relationships X1 ranked first in terms of relative importance, amounting to (72%), and came second after X3 rewards, as the relative importance reached (70.6%). As for goals, X2 has It ranked third with a relative importance of (69.8%).

Table (5) Ranking the importance of organizational culture

Dimensions	Weighted arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Relative importance	Rankings
X1 relationships	3.550	1.14	0.32	72%	The first
Goals X2	3.45	1.19	0.35	69.8%	The third
X3 rewards	3.547	1.11	0.31	70.6%	The second
Overall average	3.516	1.147	0.327	70.8%	

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on Excel

- Description and diagnosis of the dependent variable (Green Supply Chain Y)

Through table (6), we see that the descriptive statistics of the approved study variable (the green supply chain), noting that the hypothetical arithmetic mean of the scale of (3) was relied on mainly to know the extent of the research sample's awareness of the research variables, as shown below:

a. Green Purchase Y1: Respondents have been asked items in this dimension. It appears from table (6) that the weighted arithmetic mean of all items after the green purchase was higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3). Paragraph (1) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, reaching (3.55), with a standard deviation of (1.16), and a coefficient of variation (0.38) and the intensity of the answer (67.7%), which indicates the consistency of the research sample's answers to this paragraph. While paragraph (3) got the lowest weighted arithmetic mean, it reached (3.25), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean (3) with a standard deviation (1.14), a coefficient of difference (0.38), and the intensity of the answer (64.8%), and this indicates that the green purchase has Increasing and significant importance in the researched organization. While the total weighted arithmetic mean for the green purchase dimension was (3.44) with a standard deviation of (1.15) and a coefficient of difference (0.36). It indicates that the green purchase dimension is one of the clear dimensions of the sample. This indicates that the green purchasing dimension is well available in the researched organization.

B. Green Manufacturing Y2: We see from Table (6) that the total weighted arithmetic mean of the green manufacturing dimension was (3.41) with a standard deviation of (1.65) and a coefficient of difference (0.34). It was found that the weighted arithmetic mean is greater than the mean of the measurement tool. The intensity of the answer for the research sample individuals was (67.6%), and this indicates that the green manufacturing dimension is one of the clear dimensions for the research sample individuals as it is one of the important dimensions of the green supply chain, as it indicates that the sample has conviction with the interest of those in charge of obtaining green manufacturing technology. It is noted from table (4) that the weighted arithmetic mean of all paragraphs after green manufacturing was higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3). Paragraph (3) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, reaching (3.75), with a standard deviation of (1.19), and a coefficient of variation (0.31) and the intensity of the answer (74.4%), which indicates the consistency of the research sample's answers to this paragraph.

c. Green Marketing Y3: The weighted arithmetic mean for the green marketing dimension was (3.59). The value of the arithmetic mean is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean, and this indicates that the organization has a green marketing policy directed towards increasing the chances of success and providing the final solution to meet the needs of customers. The sample's answers were distinguished regarding this dimension. In a kind of convergence, this is supported by the fact that the value of the standard deviation was (1.17), which indicates the convergence of the views of the research sample regarding the aforementioned dimension. The intensity of the answer was (71.8%). It is noted in this table that the weighted arithmetic mean for all items after green marketing is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3), and paragraph (5) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, as it amounted to (3.73), with a standard deviation of (1.19), a coefficient of difference (0.32), and the intensity of the answer (74.6%), which indicates the consistency of the research sample's answers to this paragraph. While paragraph (4) got the highest weighted arithmetic mean, it reached (67.2%), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean (3) with a standard deviation (1.21), a coefficient of difference (0.36), and the intensity of the answer (67.2%), and this indicates that the organization works to prepare the required green marketing programs with excellent effectiveness.

Dr. Green Design Y4: The weighted arithmetic mean of the green design dimension was (3.41) with a standard deviation of (1.14) and a coefficient of difference (0.33). This indicates that the dimension of green design is one of the clear dimensions for the sample members, as it indicates the involvement of the research subject organization on the number of green designs in line with the organization's orientations for environmental sustainability and according to the green supply chain variable. While the arithmetic mean of all paragraphs after the green design is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean (3), as paragraph (1) obtained the highest weighted arithmetic mean, as it reached (3.67) with a standard deviation (1.13), a coefficient of difference (0.31), and the intensity of the answer (73.4%) in While paragraph (3) obtained the lowest weighted arithmetic mean, it reached (3.09), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean (3), with a standard deviation (1.12), a coefficient of difference (0.36), and the intensity of the answer (61.8%).

At the macro level, the green supply chain variable achieved a weighted arithmetic mean of (3.46). The value of the arithmetic mean is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean, which means in actual terms the strength of the availability of green supply chain dimensions in the

research community organizations, and what supports that is that the standard deviation amounted to (1.156).) which is a small value indicating the convergence of the answers of the research sample regarding the aforementioned variable, and the intensity of the response was (68.58%).

Table (6) Description and diagnosis of the Y green supply chain

	Questions	Arithmetic mean	Severity of the answer	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation
1	Q11	3.55	67.6%	1.16	0.38
2	Q12	3.58	70.4%	1.15	0.33
3	Q13	3.25	64.8%	1.14	0.36
4	Q14	3.37	67.8%	1.15	0.34
Y1	Green purchaseY 1	3.44	67.7%	1.15	0.36
1	Q15	3.3	65.6%	1.14	0.35
2	Q16	3.35	67.8%	1.17	0.36
3	Q17	3.75	74.4%	1.19	0.31
4	Q18	3.25	62.5%	1.16	0.34
Y2	Green manufacturing Y 2	3.38	67.6%	1.15	0.34
1	Q19	3.59	71.5%	1.23	0.35
2	Q20	3.63	72.0%	1.15	0.32
3	Q21	3.72	74.1%	1.15	0.31
Y3	Green marketing Y 3	3.59	71.8%	1.17	0.327
1	Q22	3.69	73.5%	1.14	0.32
2	Q23	3.12	61.6%	1.15	0.37
3	Q24	3.46	69.7%	1.16	0.35
Y4	Green design Y 4	3.41	68.3%	1.14	0.335
Y	Green processing seriesY	3.42	68.5%	1.15	0.34

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on Excel

Table (7) shows the arrangement of the dimensions of the green supply chain based on relative importance. The green procurement dimension ranked first in terms of relative importance, reaching (72.7%), and came second after green marketing, with relative importance reaching (71.8%). Green design ranked third in terms of relative importance, amounting to (68.3%), and after green manufacturing, it ranked fourth and last, with relative importance amounting to (67.6%).

Table (7) Ranking the importance of the green supply chain

Dimensions	Weighted arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Relative importance	Rankings
Green purchaseY1	3.44	1.15	0.36	72.7%	The first
Green manufacturingY2	3.41	1.65	0.34	67.6%	The fourth
Green marketing Y3	3.59	1.17	0.327	71.8%	The second
Green design Y4	3.41	1.14	0.335	68.3%	The third
Overall average	3.46	1.28	0.34	70.1%	

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on Excel

3. Hypotheses Test:-

- The main hypothesis: (There is no significant influence relationship of the organizational culture in the green supply chain).

We note through Table (8) and given the statistical indicators to test the hypotheses between the organizational culture and the green supply chain. It achieved the calculated t-value of the estimated model (40.3007) at a significant level (0.000), and this indicates the significance of the marginal tendency of the organizational culture variable. There is a significant influence relationship of organizational culture in the green supply chain. As we can see from the table, the value of the marginal tendency coefficient for the organizational culture variable was (0.866), and this indicates that increasing the organizational culture variable by one unit will lead to an increase in the green supply chain by (86.6%). The results also showed that the effect size (f²) for the organizational culture variable was large, as it recorded a value of (2.9554), which is greater than (0.36). (74.75%) of the changes that occur in the green supply chain, while the remaining percentage is related to other variables that are not included in the research model.

Table (8) Estimates of the influence of the organizational culture model in promoting the green supply chain

The independent variable	The dependent variable	Impact value The valueB	Calculated t	Moral level	² R	² F
Organizational culture	Green processing chain	0.864	40.3004	0.0000	0.7472	2.9551

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on SmartPLS software

Conclusions: -

- 1- It is clear from the description of the research sample that the researched organizations rely heavily on males in terms of gender because of the masculine nature of societies in developing countries, including the research sample.
- 2- The dimension of creativity, relationships, which is one of the dimensions of the independent variable, organizational culture, obtained the highest percentage of the rest of the dimensions, as the relative importance reached 72%, which indicates that the researched organizations attach great importance to this dimension, which is a good indicator. Then, successively, in relative importance, after the objectives.
- 3- While the green procurement dimension came in the first place within the dimensions of the dependent variable, which is the green supply chain, as it obtained 72.7% of the relative importance, while the green marketing dimension came in the second rank of relative importance, reaching 71.8%, while the rest of the dimensions came in succession. In terms of relative importance, they are both the green design dimension and the green manufacturing dimension, and this is a good indication that the surveyed organizations attach great importance to the green supply chain variable.
- 4- The strength of the influence of the organizational culture variable, which is the independent variable, reached 84.2% in the dependent variable, the green supply chain, which indicates the strength of the impact of this variable on the strategic creativity of the researched organizations.
- 5- While the strength of the effect of the rewards dimension, which is one of the dimensions of the independent variable organizational culture, reached 85.05% in the dependent variable, the green supply chain, as it came first in influence, which indicates that the researched organizations have an excellent rewards system.
- 6- While the rest of the dimensions came, including the relationship dimension and the goals dimension, and they are among the dimensions of the independent variable, organizational culture, successively, with a strong influence on the dependent variable, the green supply chain.

Recommendations:-

- 1- The need to expand the participation of women in the fields of work in society in general, and in particular in the organizations examined, in order to achieve a balance between the groups of society
- 2- Work to increase the proportion of some of the older age groups to ensure the availability of an element of experience, expertise and knowledge accumulation to ensure that the researched organizations achieve their goals.
- 3- The need to work on increasing the proportion of the dimension of goals as one of the dimensions of pivotal and increasing importance in contemporary time due to technological developments and other fields of knowledge to ensure the adaptation of the researched organizations within their environment in which they operate.
- 4- The need to strengthen the dimension of rewards because of its great importance in organizations in general and industrial organizations in particular in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage and outperform the rest of the competing organizations.
- 5- The need to strengthen the green manufacturing dimension because of its great importance in organizations in general and industrial organizations in particular, especially since it came last in the relative importance of the dimensions of the dependent variable of the green supply chain.
- 6- It is good to have green procurement, as it ranked first in the dimensions of the dependent variable of the green supply chain, as it is the cornerstone of environmental sustainability implementation.
- 7- The need to strengthen the green design dimension within the dimensions of the dependent variable of the green supply chain, because it is one of the important dimensions in accomplishing the tasks adopted by organizations, especially industrial organizations in the research environment.

References

- 1- Abdrahamane, Kone, Salia Sinaly Traore , Aly Yorote,2019, Descriptive Analysis of the Relationship between Supply Chain
- 2- Abdrahamane, Kone, Li Quan Xi, Bah Boubacar alpha, Traore Salia sinaly,2018, Empirical analysis of the relationship between Supply Chain Management and business performance: Case of companies in the cotton sector in Mali, European Journal of Business and Management ,Vol.10, No.30.
- 3- Abuzaid, Ahmad Nasser,2014, The Effect of Supply Chain Management Practices on Strategic Flexibility: Applied Study on the Jordanian Manufacturing Companies, European Journal of Business and Management ,Vol.6, No.5.
- 4- Al-Madi, Faisal,2017, The Impact of Supply Chain Management Practices on Supply Chain Performance in the Jordanian Industrial Sector, European Journal of Business and Management Vol.9, No.15.
- 5- Bagga, S. K., Gera, S., & Haque, S. N. (2022). The mediating role of organizational culture: Transformational leadership and change management in virtual teams. *Asia Pacific Management Review*.
- 6- Chin, Thoo Ai, Nurul Farah Izzati Ab Malik, Huam Hon Tat, Zuraidah Sulaiman,2020, Green Purchasing Practices and Environmental
- 7- Customer Loyalty, European Journal of Business and Management ,Vol.8, No.21

- 8- D'Angelo, V., Cappa, F., & Peruffo, E. (2023). Green manufacturing for sustainable development: The positive effects of green activities, green investments, and non-green products on economic performance. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(4), 1900-1913.
- 9- Diaz, Annika E. Jave, Ping, Cheng Guo, 2018, Internal Green Supply Chain Management Practices Influence on Firm Performance, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.10, No.33.
- 10- Dubey, Rameshwar, Surajit Bag, Sadia Samar Ali, V.G. Venkatesh, 2013, Green purchasing is key to superior performance: an empirical study, *Int. J. Procurement Management*, Vol. 6, No. 2.
- 11- *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.7, No.13.
- 12- Fachruddin, Mahnizar, Sri Yanti, Indrayani, 2020, Effects of Organizational Culture, Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance with Leadership as Intervening Variables in Tanjungpinang District, *European Journal of Business and Management* ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online)
- 13- Ferine, K. F., Aditia, R., & Rahmadana, M. F. (2021). An empirical study of leadership, organizational culture, conflict, and work ethic in determining work performance in Indonesia's education authority. *Heliyon*, 7(7), e07698.
- 14- Ferine, K. F., Aditia, R., & Rahmadana, M. F. (2021). An empirical study of leadership, organizational culture, conflict, and work ethic in determining work performance in Indonesia's education authority. *Heliyon*, 7(7), e07698.
- 15- Fritz, M. M. (2022). A supply chain view of sustainability management. *Cleaner Production Letters*, 3, 100023.
- 16- Intervening Variable, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.11, No.12.
- 17- Ismail, I. J., Amani, D., & Changalima, I. A. Strategic Green Marketing Orientation and Environmental Sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa: Does Green Absorptive Capacity Moderate? Evidence from Tanzania. Evidence from Tanzania. ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online) Vol.12, No.12.
- 19- Junaidi, Maqsood Husain, 2017, Customer Satisfaction on Supply Chain Management Practices: A Study of Toyota and Tata Motors in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, *European Journal of Business and Management*
- 20- Kanyuiro, Stanley Gitari, Maina, Samuel, 2020, The Mediating Effect of Firm Characteristics on the Relationship Between Green Marketing and Sustainability Performance: A Critical Review of the Literature and Research Agenda, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.12, No.36.
- 21- Kareem, J., Patrick, H. A., Tantia, V., & Valarmathi, S. (2022). Dataset exploring organizational culture of K-12 schools. *Data in Brief*, 42, 108179.
- 22- Ketprapakorn, N., & Kantabutra, S. (2022). Toward an organizational theory of sustainability culture. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*.
- 23- Ketprapakorn, N., & Kantabutra, S. (2022). Toward an organizational theory of sustainability culture. *Sustainable production and consumption*.
- 24- Lagat, Charles, Josphine Koech, Ambrose Kemboi, 2016, Supply Chain Management Practices, Customer Satisfaction and

- 25- Lin, H., Lin, J., & Wang, F. (2022). An innovative machine learning model for supply chain management. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(4), 100276.
- 26- Management and Business Performance: Evidence from Mali, *European Journal of Business and Management* Vol. 11, No.15
- 27- Mandi, Hironimus Efendi, Harsono, Sunardi, 2019, The Effect of Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment on the Employee Performance Through Organizational Citizenship Behavior, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.11, No.12,
- 28- Naveed, R. T., Alhaidan, H., Al Halbusi, H., & Al-Swidi, A. K. (2022). Do organizations really evolve? The critical link between organizational culture and organizational innovation toward organizational effectiveness: Pivotal role of organizational resistance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(2), 100178.
- 29- Naveed, R. T., Alhaidan, H., Al Halbusi, H., & Al-Swidi, A. K. (2022). Do organizations really evolve? The critical link between organizational culture and organizational innovation toward organizational effectiveness: Pivotal role of organizational resistance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(2), 100178.
- 30- Njoku, (MRS) M. E, O.U, Kalu ALEXANDA, 2015, Effective Supply Chain Management: A Strategic Tool for Profitability Enhancement in the Competitive Marketing Environment (An Empirical Evidence in the Nigerian Food and Beverage Industry 2005 - 2014),
- 31- Obi, Chris Jojo, Xiong Qiang, Courage Simon Kofi Dogbe, Wisdom, Wise Kwabla Pomegbe, 2020, Assessing the Impact of Relational Governance on the Supply Chain Performances of Manufacturing Firms in Ghana, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.12, No.12.
- 32- Paul, I. D., Bhole, G. P., & Chaudhari, J. R. (2014). A review on green manufacturing: it's important, methodology and its application. *Procedia materials science*, 6, 1644-1649.
- 33- Performance, *Int. J Sup. Chain. Mgt* Vol. 9, No. 1.
- 34- Prieto-Sandoval, V., Torres-Guevara, L. E., & García-Díaz, C. (2022). Green marketing innovation: Opportunities from an environmental education analysis in young consumers. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 363, 132509.
- 35- Ramadiyanto, Yasananda Khusnul, Augustine, Yvonne, 2019, Perishable Food Supply Chain, Supply of Chain Management on Risk Mitigation with Enterprise Risk Management as an
- 36- Rass, L., Treur, J., Kucharska, W., & Wiewiora, A. (2023). Adaptive Dynamical Systems Modelling of Transformational Organizational Change with Focus on Organizational Culture and Organizational Learning. *Cognitive Systems Research*.
- 37- Rodríguez-González, R. M., Maldonado-Guzmán, G., Madrid-Guijarro, A., & Garza-Reyes, J. A. (2022). Does circular economy affect financial performance? The mediating role of sustainable supply chain management in the automotive industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379, 134670..
- 38- Saini, N., Malik, K., & Sharma, S. (2023). Transformation of Supply Chain Management to Green Supply Chain Management: Certain Investigations for Research and Applications. *Cleaner Materials*, 100172.
- 39- Srikaningsih, Ana, Setyadi, Djoko, 2015, The Effect of Competence and Motivation and Cultural Organization towards Organizational Commitment and Performance on State

- University Lecturers in East Kalimantan Indonesia, *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.7, No.17.
- 40- Ullah, M., Zahid, M., Rizvi, S. M. A. E. R., Qureshi, Q. G. M., & Ali, F. (2022). Do green supply chain management practices improve organizational resilience during the COVID-19 crisis? A survival analysis of global firms. *Economics Letters*, 219, 110802. Vol.12, No.21.
- 41- Weeratunge, R.A.D. Dillanjani, Herath, Renuka, 2018, THE DIMENSIONS OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES, *World Conference on Supply Chain Management*, Vol. 4, Issue 1.
- 42- Yuan, Q., & Tang, L. Y. (2021). The Principles in Green Design. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 259, p. 02002). EDP Sciences.
- 43- Zhang, Q., Gao, B., & Luqman, A. (2022). Linking green supply chain management practices with competitiveness during covid 19: The role of big data analytics. *Technology in Society*, 70, 102021.